

ELIXIR Training Platform WP3

M3.11 Training Coordinator (TrC) Terms of Reference

Tier: Technology
Thematic Area: Training

Executive Summary

The milestone M3.11 contributes to the development of an inclusive and standardised framework of guidelines and role definitions for the ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP). It presents a draft Terms of Reference (ToR) for Training Coordinators (TrCs), building on previous WP3 milestones and deliverables, as well as sustained work within the TrP and the Training Coordinators' Group (TrCG).

The ToR defines the TrC role from both Node and ELIXIR-wide perspectives, clarifying responsibilities, governance, communication channels, support and recognition mechanisms, and interactions with other ELIXIR Platforms and external infrastructures. By formalising these elements, the milestone aims to strengthen operational coherence, support onboarding, and ensure alignment between Node-level training activities and ELIXIR's strategic objectives.

This milestone will be shared with TrCs for feedback and refined as needed to produce the final TrC ToR deliverable. Nodes are expected to adopt the ToR while supplementing it with Node-specific expectations where required. The ToR should be periodically reviewed and updated, incorporating feedback from Nodes to reflect evolving ELIXIR strategy, governance, and infrastructure interactions.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TrP	Training Platform
TrC(s)	Training Coordinator(s)
ToR	Terms of References
HoN	Head of Node
TrCG	Training Coordinator Group

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Purpose and Objectives

The purpose of this Terms of Reference (ToR) document is to define the role, scope, responsibilities, and governance of the ELIXIR Training Coordinators (TrCs) across ELIXIR Nodes. It aims to ensure a clear, transparent, and standardised understanding of the TrC role both from the Node perspective and the ELIXIR Hub perspective.

TrC is the key liaison between national ELIXIR Nodes and the ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP) and forms the Training Coordinators Group (TrCG). The role aims to ensure clarity, transparency, and consistency in expectations, while supporting onboarding, recognition, and active participation across the platform.

This ToR supports ELIXIR's overarching goal of strengthening capacity-building, coordination, and sustainability of training strategy and activities. It contributes to developing an inclusive and harmonised framework for training standards and activities, thereby facilitating onboarding and ensuring operational competence.

This document is part of Activity 2 in TrP WP3, and is aligned with ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 efforts to strengthen Node staff capacities and promote shared operational standards across the infrastructure.

Scope and Applicability of the ToR

The ToR applies to all ELIXIR Nodes and provides a shared, coherent framework for how TrCs operate within their national context and within the wider ELIXIR ecosystem. Building on the ELIXIR Strategy¹ and the activities coordinated through the TrP Leadership Team, it clarifies the objectives, expectations, and working principles that guide the TrC role. The ToR defines how TrCs contribute to their Node, how they engage across Nodes, and how they collaborate with the ELIXIR Hub and the TrP to support a coordinated and sustainable training landscape.

Training Coordinator Role and Dual Responsibilities

A Training Coordinator (TrC) is the designated representative responsible for linking Node-level training activities with ELIXIR's training strategy. TrCs coordinate national training efforts with the ELIXIR TrP, ensuring that local expertise, priorities, and opportunities are aligned with ELIXIR-wide objectives². They contribute to strategic planning, support the implementation of training initiatives, and facilitate information exchange between their Node and the TrP.

¹ ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028 <https://elixir-europe.org/sites/default/files/documents/elixir-programme-24-28-full.pdf>

² D3.5 Overview of the critical components of the TrP network and relevant resources for TrCs and TrP Node members, [D3.5 Report Critical Components TrP.docx](#) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258955>

The TrC role has dual responsibilities; representing the interests and capabilities of their Node while also advancing the shared goals of the ELIXIR TrP. TrCs ensure that Node activities contribute to the coherence of ELIXIR's training landscape, and in turn, they bring ELIXIR-wide developments, standards, and opportunities back to their Node. Each ELIXIR Node designates one or more TrCs to serve as the primary interface between the Node and the ELIXIR TrP. In this role, TrCs represent their Node within the TrCG and TrP coordination activities, support governance and planning processes, and act as a liaison between Node training staff and ELIXIR structures³. This includes mapping and reporting Node-level training activities, communicating updates and needs to the ELIXIR Hub as requested, and supporting mechanisms for recognising training contributions.

Collective Coordination of Training Across ELIXIR Nodes

TrCs from all ELIXIR Nodes collectively form the TrCG. Each Node is represented by one TrC, ensuring full Node coverage across ELIXIR. The TrCG operates under ELIXIR Hub guidance, specifically the Programme Manager responsible for the Training Platform, ensuring strategic guidance and coordination between Training Platform and Training Coordinators efforts TrCs are accountable to their respective Head of Node (HoN) and, collectively, contribute to ELIXIR-wide coordination through the TrCG, with strategic oversight from the ELIXIR Hub.

The TrCG serves as a collaborative network that promotes coordination, knowledge exchange, and alignment of training activities across Nodes. TrCs represent and showcase their Node's training activities and expertise, including trainers, resources, tools, and services, while fostering cross-Node collaborations and joint initiatives.

The TrCG meets regularly, through virtual calls complemented by annual face-to-face (F2F) meetings. Ongoing communication is supported via established ELIXIR channels, including mailing lists and collaborative platforms (e.g., Slack)³. Subgroups or task forces may be established to address specific topics.

Reporting and feedback are integral to TrCG operations. Training activities, challenges, and key metrics (e.g., number of courses, participants, and FAIR compliance) are shared between the TrCG, the TrP leadership, and the ELIXIR Hub to support monitoring, planning, and continuous improvement.

Engagement with the ELIXIR Hub and ELIXIR-Wide Structures

Effective coordination within ELIXIR depends on clear communication channels, shared understanding of roles, and strong integration between Nodes and central structures. TrCs operate at the interface of national and ELIXIR-wide activities; therefore, understanding how to engage with the ELIXIR Hub and related organisational structures is essential for ensuring coherent and high-

³ M3.10 Report on current practices for Training Coordinators and TrP Node members (in relation to activities and onboarding), highlight areas for recognition, and redefine the existing onboarding process -[M3.10 Current Practices TrC TrP](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258995), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258995>

impact training provision across the infrastructure. The following subsections outline how TrCs interact with the ELIXIR Hub and other ELIXIR structures, and describe the support mechanisms available to them.

Interaction with ELIXIR Hub

ELIXIR has a responsibility to promote and facilitate collaboration between Nodes to enhance training coordination, exchange best practices, and support capacity building. Within this ecosystem, the ELIXIR Hub plays a central role in supporting the work of TrCs by offering coordination, documentation, and operational alignment for jointly agreed actions. As described in the ELIXIR TrC role definition [to be available in the updated ELIXIR Handbook of Operations, to be published soon], ensures that activities are properly connected to ELIXIR's strategic objectives and in that realm, Nodes receive the guidance needed to implement their training responsibilities.

Upon formal appointment from a Node, the Hub ensures that a TrC is officially registered across ELIXIR communication and governance channels, including the TrC mailing list, weekly brief, official ELIXIR TrCG webpage⁴, and internal organisational records. This onboarding process ensures that the new TrC has visibility within the network and can engage with ongoing initiatives without delay. These channels also form the backbone of ongoing communications and external relations, ensuring sustained interaction and information flow across ELIXIR.

The Hub also supports strategic planning and decision-making related to training by facilitating consultation and coordinating discussions across relevant Platforms, Communities, Focus Groups and other relevant stakeholders. This helps align Node-level activities to ELIXIR's long-term training strategy and ensures that developments are consistent across Europe. Close collaboration with the TrP ensures coherence between coordination, policy development, and operational delivery of training. TrCs are encouraged to engage with the ELIXIR Handbook of Operations⁵, which provides key guidance in the following areas:

- **ELIXIR purpose, identity, and values;** understanding the mission and strategic positioning of ELIXIR within the life-science data ecosystem helps TrCs ensure that their training activities reflect ELIXIR's commitment to openness, interoperability, sustainability, and community building.
- **Operational structure of ELIXIR;** It explains how Nodes, Platforms, Communities, Focus Groups, and the Hub interact. It clarifies reporting lines, decision-making pathways, and operational processes, enabling TrCs to navigate ELIXIR structures efficiently and identify where their work contributes within the broader framework.
- **Communications and External Relations;** The Handbook describes all supported communication channels. TrCs are expected to actively use these channels to disseminate

⁴ Training Coordinators (webpage by ELIXIR Europe) <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/trcg>

⁵ ELIXIR Handbook of Operations, most up to date version linked from here: <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>. 2025 (PDF Document)

training opportunities, coordinate with fellow TrCs, engage external stakeholders, and remain informed of strategic and operational developments.

- **Recognition and Support for TrCs;** it is important for ELIXIR to recognise sustained engagement in the TrC role and understand that it requires visible acknowledgement and practical support. Acknowledging individual and collective efforts ensures that the work of trainers and coordinators is visible and valued, not only within the TrP, but also across ELIXIR and partner EOSC/ESFRI organisations. Mechanisms of recognition for TrCs can include formal acknowledgement of the role within ELIXIR governance, visibility through ELIXIR communication channels, opportunities to contribute to strategic deliverables and reports, and participation in ELIXIR-wide training events and coordination meetings. These mechanisms help TrCs maintain the role over time and its strategic importance.
- **Support from the TrP and the ELIXIR Hub;** The TrP and Hub provide coordinated support to TrCs through access to shared training resources, best-practice guidelines, training catalogues, planning and reporting frameworks, and direct assistance from Hub staff. This support reduces duplication of effort, strengthens alignment across Nodes, and enables TrCs to focus on community building and capacity development.

Interaction with other ELIXIR Structures

TrCs interact with ELIXIR-wide infrastructures to ensure that training activities are aligned with ELIXIR's overall strategy and benefit from cross-domain expertise. For example, TrCs may collaborate with other ELIXIR Platforms (Data, Tools, Compute, and Interoperability) on cross-platform training initiatives that address shared priorities, emerging needs, and integrated service provision. TrCs also have opportunities to collaborate with ELIXIR Communities such as Research Data Management Community and domain-specific Communities.

TrCs may also engage with external partners, including research infrastructures, projects, and initiatives within the EOSC and ESFRI landscape. Such interactions can include contributing to partnerships, co-organising joint workshops, and participating in EU-funded projects related to training. These activities support alignment with ELIXIR's strategic objectives, strengthen interoperability across infrastructures, and enhance the sustainability and visibility of ELIXIR training efforts, as outlined in D3.5².

Through these dual interactions, TrCs help position ELIXIR training within a broader European context, ensuring coherence across platforms and effective collaboration with external stakeholders while maintaining a clear link to Node-level expertise and priorities.

Conclusion

By defining who TrCs are, how they operate, and how they interact across ELIXIR, the ToR aims to enhance transparency, strengthen engagement, and ensure the long-term sustainability of TrP operations. It supports a coherent and collaborative environment in which TrCs can efficiently represent their Nodes, share good practices, and collectively advance ELIXIR's training mission. We hope this milestone provides TrC personnel a foundational understanding on how to engage with

ELIXIR and its strategy, in order to have successful interactions and build national training strategy and capacity building with respective Node members involved in training.

Supporting Documents

[Handbook of Operation v 7.3](#)

see: <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258995>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17252853>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258955>

Commented [1]: All these have already been referenced, so this is a duplication.

Dissemination Plans

This document will be available in Zenodo under the Training Platform 2024-2026 work plan [library](#).

Commented [2]: There is no such library on Zenodo, maybe the intention was to refer to Zotero